

TRÆNGER DU TIL AT
FÅ LADET OP??

SÅ TAG EN
PAUSE HER...

NEED A BREAK??
HAVE A CHIT CHAT...

SOLCELLETRÆET THE SOLAR TREE

Solcelletræet LÆS MENS DU VENTER!

GRATIS Strøm!

Solcelletræet

Består af et metallskelet og en metalrod. Stammen er beklædt med en træstamme af Douglasgran og kronen består af 8 bagegrene. Bladene er lavet af spånplade beklædt med solceller. Solcellerne producerer strøm til kontakten på stammen, som du gratis kan bruge.

Traer og bæredygtig energi

Træ er et af de mest bæredygtige råstoffer der findes fordi træ er en fornybar ressource i modsætning til kul og olie, og fordi det bruges færre sprøjtemidler i træproduktionen end til de fleste andre landbrugsafgrøder. Træer omdanner sollys, vand, CO₂ og næringsstoffer fra jorden til vedmasse, som kan bruges til byggeri, møbler, brændte, flis til kraftværker, papir – ja, mulighederne er nærmest uendelige. I løbet af nogle år vil man sandsynligvis også kunne hælde træbaseret brændstof i tanken på sin bil.

Traer og klima

Skove og træer spiller en vigtig rolle i forhold til at modvirke klimaforandringer fordi de optager CO₂ fra atmosfæren og omdanner det til vedmasse. Træer optager CO₂ så længe de gror, og de kan gro i mange år, og de lagrer også CO₂ efter at de er færdige og brugt til et møbel. Så længe verdens skove vokser fjernes der CO₂ fra atmosfæren, men hvis den globale skovrydning overstiger tilvæksten medvirker det til CO₂-udledning. Det er derfor vigtigt, at verdens skovressourcerbevares og forages.

Solenergi

Solenergi er en vedvarende energikilde, som ikke kun træer og andre planter kan finde ud af at udnytte. Solenergi vil ifølge Energistyrelsen potentielt kunne dække op mod 1/3 af verdens energiforbrug, men er dog stadig relativt dyrt.

Hvis du vil lære mere

Om solceller og elektronikken bag eller om bygningskonstruktion overvej en uddannelse på DTU-Elektro eller DTU-Byg. Om skovbrug, bæredygtig forvaltning af naturressourcer eller hvordan man laver træer om til bioenergi så overvej en uddannelse på Skov & Landskab under Københavns Universitet

The solar tree READ WHILE YOU WAIT

FREE electricity!

Facts about the solar tree

The solar tree consists of a metal foot and stem which is covered by a log of Douglas fir. The crown consists of 8 branches to which the leaves with solarpanels are attached. The solar panels produce electricity which you freely can use.

Trees and sustainable energy

Wood is one of the most sustainable raw materials because it is a renewable resource as opposed to coal and oil, and because significantly less pesticides are used for its production than for other agricultural products. Trees convert sunlight, water, CO₂ and nutrients from the ground to wood, which can be used for buildings, furniture, firewood both in small and large scale, paper, etc. – the possibilities are almost endless. Within a few years it will probably be possible to pour wood based fuel on your car.

Trees and climate change

Forests and trees are playing an important part in terms of climate change mitigation because they absorb CO₂ from the atmosphere. Trees absorb CO₂ as long as they grow, and they can grow for many years, and they store the absorbed CO₂ also after they are cut down and transformed to e.g. a chair. As long as the world's forests grow, CO₂ is removed from the atmosphere, but if the global deforestation exceeds the growth rate it adds to amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere. Therefore it is important that the global forest resources are protected and increased.

Solar energy

Solar energy is a sustainable energy source, which not only trees and other plants know how to use. According to the Danish Energy Agency the potential for solar energy is enormous, as it potentially could provide for 1/3 of the world's energy consumption. However, solar energy is still more costly than other energy technologies.

If you want to learn more

About solar panels and the electronics that make them work, or about the construction of buildings (or solar trees :) than consider taking an education at DTU – Electrical engineering or DTU-Civil Engineering at DTU – Technical University of Denmark. About forestry, sustainable management of natural resources or how to turn wood into bio fuel, then consider an education at Forest & Landscape, Denmark at University of Copenhagen

SPONSORS

The Technical University of Denmark (DTU) has contributed from two institutes: DTU Electrical Engineering, which has sponsored labor and DTU Civil Engineering which has contributed to the construction of the metal parts of the tree Danish Forestry College under Forest & Landscape, Denmark, which is an institute under University of Copenhagen (KU) has sponsored the Douglas fir log and the branches. Sunsil has sponsored the solar panels.

Other materials are paid for by Roskilde Festival. The tree is developed and built by: Thomas Andersen, Arnold Knott, DTU Electrical Engineering, Jens Martin Dandanell, DTU Civil Engineering and Dorthe Lund, Forest & Landscape, Denmark, KU, who are thankful for all the support and help they have recieved. The poster is designed by: www.g-design.dk.

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